

**SITUATIONAL ANALYSIS OF DIPHTHERIA EPIDEMICS IN NIGER (2022-2024):
FINDINGS, IMPLICATIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Diphtheria made a sudden reappearance in Niger in 2022. **Objective:** To describe the clinical, epidemiological, and evolutionary aspects of the diphtheria epidemics in Niger from 2022-2024. **Method:** A retrospective analysis was conducted on epidemiological and clinical surveillance data reported during the study period. **Results:** Over 3 years of surveillance, a worrying escalation in number of cases was observed, from 634 in 2022 to 4,002 in 2024 with a total of 8,047 suspected and 518 deaths recorded. Geographically, the epidemic spread from three initial regions to almost the entire country in two years. Demographic analysis identifies children aged 5 to 14 as the most vulnerable group, although all age groups are affected. Clinically, while sore throat and fever are predominant symptoms, the presence of pseudomembranes remains a critical warning sign. This seasonal dynamic, with a peak between August and October, underscores the urgency of strengthening vaccination coverage, early diagnostic capabilities, communication and community engagement to break the chain of transmission.

KEYWORDS: Diphtheria; epidemiology; clinical; Niger.

INTRODUCTION

Diphtheria, caused by *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, primarily affects the upper respiratory tract and can lead to the formation of a thick, gray membrane in the throat.^[1,2,3] Once considered controlled through extensive vaccination programs^[4,5], diphtheria is experiencing an alarming resurgence in West Africa, particularly in Niger.^[5,6] Sporadic cases and outbreaks of diphtheria have been reported in recent decades, especially in areas with disrupted health systems and low vaccination rates.^[7,8] These outbreaks have been associated with significant morbidity and mortality, particularly among unvaccinated children and adolescents, and highlight the persistent vulnerability of certain African communities to this ancient disease.^[1,2,6,9] Historically, diphtheria was

one of the most significant infections with the highest mortality rate in children, causing large epidemics worldwide. In Niger, diphtheria has remained endemic, with sporadic cases recorded in nomadic areas.^[10] This serious infectious disease is no longer limited to isolated outbreaks but is becoming a major public health challenge. Since 2022, the country has been facing a complex epidemic dynamic, exacerbated by fragile socio-sanitary contexts.^[11,12] Although surveillance efforts have intensified, the scale of the current transmission requires a thorough analysis of recent epidemiological trends. This article aims to examine the epidemiological situation between January 2022 and October 2024, highlighting the spatio-temporal evolution of cases and the predominant clinical profiles.

The objective is to provide a solid evidence base to reorient response strategies and prevent the disease from becoming endemic.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study conducted was a retrospective descriptive and analytical study covering the period from January 1, 2022, to October 31, 2024. It was based on aggregated national epidemiological surveillance data of all suspected diphtheria cases notified in Niger to the Ministry of Health. The variables studied included cases and deaths, case fatality rate, spatial dynamics, temporal variation, age distribution, and disease-specific incidence. The clinical data analyzed included the most common clinical signs. Data analysis was descriptive and included the calculation of the case fatality rate, spatial analyses, and a trend analysis, highlighting changes in

cases, deaths, and the case fatality rate over time. The study adhered to ethical guidelines by using only aggregated and centralized data, without any identifying or individual information. It allowed for the description of the epidemiological and clinical characteristics of the diphtheria epidemic, highlighting trends, and formulating explanatory hypotheses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The epidemiology of diphtheria in Niger between 2022 and 2024 shows an increase in cases, deaths, and case fatality rate over the years. Niger reported 8,047 cases of diphtheria between January 2022 and October 2024, with a significant increase in cases from 634 in 2022 to 4,002 in 2024. The number of deaths rose from 60 in 2022 to 227 in 2024, totaling 518 deaths over the study period (Table I).

Table I: Evolution of Cases, Deaths and Case Fatality Rate by Year.

Year	Reported Cases	Deaths	Case Fatality Rate (%)
2022	634	60	9.5%
2023	3411	231	6.8%
2024	4002	227	5.7%
Total	8047	518	6.43%

In terms of spatial distribution, in 2022, only three regions were affected, but by 2023, all eight regions had

cases, and in 2024, only the Dosso region had none (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Spatial dynamics of the diphtheria epidemic in Niger: incidence of reported cases by district of origin a) 2022; b) 2023; (c) 2024 (descriptive representation).

The most affected age groups were 1-4 years, 5-14 years, and 15 years and older, with a predominance

of cases in the 5-14 age group (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Distribution of reported diphtheria cases in Niger by age group.

Most cases occurred between August and October of each year (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Monthly evolution of reported annual diphtheria cases.

The most common clinical symptoms were sore throat, cough, fever, and headache, which were present in the vast majority of cases. The presence of a false

membrane, cervical swelling, and dyspnea was less frequent (Table II).

Table II: Clinical profile of diphtheria cases reported in Niger from 2022 to 2024.

Clinical Sign	Number of Cases	Percentage
Sore throat / dysphagia	6185	96.6%
Cough	5849	91.4%
Fever	5068	79.2%
Headache	3878	60.6%
False membrane	1362	21.3%
Cervical swelling/lymphadenopathy	1172	18.3%
Dyspnea	1113	17.4%
Common cold	622	9.7%
Other	224	3.5%

The rapid increase in cases in Niger is part of a regional resurgence of diphtheria. Between May 2022 and October 2023, Nigeria, Niger's neighbor, recorded 13,416 cases of diphtheria and 600 deaths. The most affected states were Kano, Yobe, Katsina, Bauchi, Borno, and Kaduna, which accounted for 95.8% of cases.^[7] Some of these states border the Zinder region,

where the 2022 diphtheria epidemic in Niger began, with the epicenter in the Gouré district, which borders Nigeria.^[12] This could explain the cross-border spread of the disease. However, the trajectory of the epidemic in Niger demonstrates a lack of initial control and an escalation of the crisis. The spread from Gouré and Tesker to Arlit, with a threefold increase in incidence

(Figure 1), indicates that the epidemic spread faster than response efforts could contain it. This may be the result of an initial underestimation of the threat, a slow response, or insufficient health infrastructure to manage a massive influx of cases. The ability to contain the spread is an indicator of the health system's resilience. The data analysis highlights a systemic vulnerability that allowed the epidemic to escalate into a national crisis. The rapid spread of the epidemic from Gouré to Arlit can be explained by population movements due to trade, nomadism, and migration.

The predominance of cases in the "one year and older" age group is a crucial finding (Figure 2). Routine childhood vaccination against diphtheria is generally administered before the age of one.^[4, 5, 13] A high incidence in older children and adolescents suggests a possible accumulation of unimmunized individuals over time. This forms a "reservoir" of susceptibility that fuels the epidemic. This underscores the need to go beyond routine vaccination programs to include catch-up campaigns targeting older children and adolescents.

The data analysis reveals a strong seasonality of cases, with annual peaks consistently occurring between August and October (Figure 3). The period from May to July, on the other hand, corresponded to the lowest number of cases (Figure 3). This trend could be linked to environmental and demographic conditions conducive to transmission, such as the rainy season, population migration and movements for agricultural or for other reasons. This seasonality implies that awareness, vaccination, and surveillance efforts should be intensified just before the peak period, between May and July, to maximize their impact on the spread.

The study of the clinical characteristics of reported cases provides essential information for improving early detection and diagnosis. Diphtheria cases most often present with a combination of general symptoms, namely fever, sore throat, cough, and headache (Table II). The analysis confirms that sore throat is the most consistent symptom, present in 96.6% of cases. Its near-ubiquity makes it a key indicator for identifying suspected cases. In contrast, the presence of a false membrane, although a pathognomonic sign of the disease, is observed in only a minority of cases, namely 21.3% (Table II). This creates a risk of underdiagnosis. If clinical surveillance criteria are based solely on the false membrane, a large majority of cases will be missed. A more effective approach for health workers and community surveillance agents is to consider every case of sore throat, especially in endemic or emerging areas, as a suspected case of diphtheria. Such an approach would allow for the initiation of rapid treatment and the triggering of contact tracing procedures, which is essential for interrupting the chain of transmission. Cervical swelling (the "bull neck" sign) and dyspnea are manifestations of more severe forms of the disease, which is consistent with their lower prevalence of 18.3% and 17.4% of cases, respectively

(Table II).

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Faced with the escalation of this health crisis, a fragmented response is doomed to fail. It is imperative to adopt an integrated and aggressive strategy, based on the evidence from this analysis. We formulate the following recommendations, not as mere suggestions, but as strategic actions to regain control of the epidemic:

- **Deployment of an Emergency "Vaccination Force."** It is crucial to go beyond routine vaccination. We call for the immediate continuation of large-scale, targeted mass vaccination campaigns. These campaigns must aggressively prioritize epidemiological "hotspots," high-mobility border areas, and, above all, the 5-14 age groups that constitute the main reservoir of the epidemic. This action must be carried out with the speed and logistics of a national emergency operation.
- **Securing and Pre-positioning Lifesaving Treatments.** Reducing mortality depends on immediate access to diphtheria antitoxin (DAT) and appropriate antibiotics. Waiting for severe cases to arrive in regional capitals is a losing strategy. It is imperative to decentralize stocks of DAT and antibiotics by pre-positioning them at the most affected and at-risk district levels, thus ensuring treatment within hours of diagnosis, not days.
- **Establishment of an "Early Warning" Surveillance System.** Passive surveillance has shown its limits. A proactive surveillance network must be activated. This involves strengthening the technical capacity of regional laboratories to reduce confirmation times from several days to less than 24 hours. In parallel, the suspected case definition must be redefined to include any febrile sore throat in epidemic areas, to trigger an immediate investigation and isolation, long before the appearance of signs of severity.
- **Launch of a Communication and Community Engagement Offensive.** The success of the response depends on the trust and cooperation of the population. A transparent and culturally appropriate communication campaign must be launched to counter misinformation and vaccine hesitancy. The messages must be clear: vaccination saves lives, and any Eye-Nose and Throat symptom (sore throat, cough) should lead to immediate consultation. The involvement of community and religious leaders is non-negotiable to ensure the support and success of this mobilization.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of the diphtheria epidemic in Niger (2022-2024) demonstrates that the disease is no longer a latent risk, but an active and expanding public health threat. The exponential increase in cases and geographical spread highlight persistent gaps in routine vaccination coverage. To reverse this trend, a simple reactive

response is no longer sufficient. It is imperative to integrate a proactive strategy combining targeted mass vaccination campaigns, securing the supply of antitoxins, and strengthening the laboratory network. The 2024 data must serve as a catalyst for coordinated action, aimed not only at addressing current outbreaks but, more importantly, at anticipating future seasonal peaks. Failure to act decisively now will only further entrench diphtheria in Niger's epidemiological landscape, with devastating consequences.

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